

Sample Name: PP Vir 1-5 μm

Material: Polypropylene

Size: 1-5 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 2,37 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- $7,9 \times 10^{12}$ particles per gram
- 39740 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C_3H_6 (PP) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
2,83	1,68	0,59	0,27	0,20	2,37	7.9×10^{12}	39740

Chemical Composition* (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C_3H_6	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	227
P	73
S	10
Cl	449
K	54
Ca	88
Ti	3
Cr	83
Mn	4
Fe	223
Ni	15
Cu	1
Zn	1
Mo	1
Pb	1

* The XRF results shown were measured on PP UV-aged material.

Chemical Bonding (Using $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ provided by TNO)**Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy** (provided by TNO)

Not available